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A Comparative Cognitive Mapping Study on Tourism Students' Perceptions of Toxic Leadership

Turizm Öğrencilerinin Toksik Liderlik Algıları Üzerine Karşılaştırmalı Bir Bilişsel Haritalama Araştırması

ABSTRACT

The concept of toxic leadership refers to a management style that exhibits destructive behavioral patterns in organizational structures and is characterized by dysfunctional personality traits. The negative effects of this type of leadership style on organizational processes and its associated costs make it necessary to examine toxic leadership systematically. The identification of toxic leadership behaviors and the analysis of their effects are critical for organizational sustainability. This study aims to examine how tourism students perceive toxic leadership behaviors in the context of cause and effect relationships. The research was designed as a qualitative case study. Cognitive mapping method was used to collect data. Laddering interview technique was used to derive cognitive maps. The maps created and data obtained from 40 students studying at Kocaeli University Faculty of Tourism in Türkiye were analysed with the Decision Explorer 3.3.0 software. Central, Cluster, Hieset, Potency and Collapse Analyses were performed on the obtained maps. The total duration of the interviews, which lasted 41 minutes on average, lasted 27 hours and 36 minutes in total. The findings reveal that leadership behaviors reducing employee motivation have the highest impact on students' perception of toxic leadership. In addition, our study shows that perceptions differed according to the department of study, gender and experiences with toxic leaders. Results are presented by drawing comparisons between cognitive models of gastronomy and culinary arts and hospitality management students with each other, the cognitive models of male and female students with each other, and finally the cognitive models of students who have and have not worked with toxic leaders before. The research contributes to the understanding of toxic leadership in the context of tourism education and the tourism sector in general.

Keywords: Toxic Leadership, Dark Side of Leadership, Cognitive Mapping, Qualitative Research, Tourism Students.

ÖZET

Toksik liderlik olgusu, örgütsel yapılarda yıkıcı davranış örüntüleri sergileyen ve işlevsiz kişilik özellikleriyle karakterize edilen bir yönetim biçimini ifade etmektedir. Bu tür liderlik tarzının örgütsel süreçler üzerindeki olumsuz etkileri ve beraberinde getirdiği maliyetler, konunun sistematik bir şekilde incelenmesini gerekli kılmaktadır. Toksik liderlik davranışlarının tanımlanması ve etkilerinin analizi, örgütsel sürdürülebilirlik açısından kritik öneme sahiptir. Bu araştırmada, turizm öğrencilerinin toksik liderlik davranışlarını neden-sonuç ilişkileri bağlamında nasıl algıladıklarını incelemek amaçlanmıştır. Araştırma nitel bir durum araştırması olarak tasarlanmış olup verilerin toplanmasında bilişsel haritalama yöntemi kullanılmıştır. Bilişsel haritaların elde edilmesinde ise basamaklı görüşme tekniği kullanılmıştır. Kocaeli Üniversitesi Turizm Fakültesi'nde öğrenim gören 40 öğrenciden elde edilen veriler Decision Explorer 3.3.0 programıyla analiz edilmiştir. Ortalama 41 dakika süren görüşmelerin toplam süresi 27 saat 36 dk. olarak raporlanmıştır. Bulgular, çalışanın motivasyonunu düşüren liderlik davranışlarının öğrencilerin toksik liderlik algısına en fazla etki ettiğini ortaya koymaktadır. Ayrıca algıların öğrenim görülen bölüm, cinsiyet ve toksik lider deneyimine göre farklılaştığı tespit edilmiştir. Araştırma, turizm öğrenimi ve sektörü bağlamında toksik liderliğin anlaşılmasına katkı sağlamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Toksik Liderlik, Karanlık Liderlik, Bilişsel Haritalama, Nitel Araştırma, Turizm Öğrencileri.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is widely accepted that organizational leadership plays a critical role in the success of businesses. In the literature, leadership studies generally focus on the positive aspects and the concept of a leader has been attributed with romanticized qualities such as high status, reputability, prestige, charisma and heroism (Bligh, 2017). Meindl & Ehrlich (1987) highlight that regardless of the actual impact of leadership on organizations and societies, leadership has an unbalanced influence on our understanding of the world. Beyond this romanticized understanding of leadership, in recent years, researchers have begun to draw attention to the dark side of leadership. In this context, the concept of "toxic leadership" offers a comprehensive approach that gathers the negative characteristics and effects of leaders under one roof.

Toxic leadership is defined as a leadership style that causes severe and permanent damage to the organization through destructive and oppressive behaviors (Lipman-Blumen, 2005). Since the structure of organizations is shaped from top to bottom, the perception of toxicity moves in a similar direction and the higher the position of the toxic leader, the more widespread the organizational damage (Appelbaum & Roy-Girard, 2007; Wilson- Starks, 2003). The economic repercussions of this situation are also striking; studies show that the annual loss of US companies due to toxic leadership alone reaches 200 billion dollars (Appelbaum & Roy-Girard, 2007).

In the labor-intensive tourism industry, especially in accommodation and food and beverage businesses, the main element of service production and delivery is human labor (Kozak et al., 2017). Therefore, negative situations that employees are exposed to directly affect service quality and customer experience. Studies show that the experiences of employees exposed to toxic leadership negatively affect the image of the sector. Therefore, it is critical to systematically examine toxic leadership behaviors and their effects in the tourism sector.

Toxic leadership studies in the current literature are mainly concentrated in education and health sectors. It is noteworthy that the studies in the field of tourism are both limited in number and generally carried out with quantitative methods. Especially the scarcity of qualitative analyses based on cause-effect relationships limits the in-depth understanding of the subject. In order to fill this gap, this study analyses tourism students' perceptions of toxic leadership using the cognitive mapping method. Understanding toxic leadership behaviors and their consequences from the perspective of students who will be the tourism professionals of the future offers important results for the sustainable development of the sector.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Toxic Leadership

The concept of toxic leadership is an approach that gathers the behaviors representing the dark side of leadership under a single roof. The concept, which was first discussed by Whicker (1996), defines toxic leaders as non-compliant, malicious and malevolent people and further highlights that these leaders tend to hide their own inadequacies (Başar et al., 2016). Lipman- Blumen (2005) defines a toxic leader as "a kind of poison that creates a substantial influential pressure on the personality of the subordinate" and states that these leaders will inevitably cause serious and permanent damage to their followers. Reed (2004) describes the toxic leader as "an insidious, slow-acting poison that is difficult to diagnose making it difficult to apply an antidote", while Flynn (1999) emphasizes that the toxic leader has "bullying, threatening, shouting" behaviors as well as a changing mood and that the toxic leader's current mood determines the climate of the organization. Wilson-Starks (2003) defines toxic leadership as "a leadership style that harms employees and ultimately the organization by poisoning enthusiasm, creativity, autonomy and expressions of innovation". According to Frost (2003), the toxic feeling created by a toxic leader is "an element that depletes the energies of individuals and damages the organization in a way that causes staff to quit". O'Hara (2015) states that the effects of toxic leadership continue even after the employee leaves the workplace and cause serious and long-term damage to both individuals and the organization. In the literature, toxic leadership dimensions are classified as follows (Schmidt, 2008; Çelebi et al., 2015; Author, 2016):

- Egocentrism
- Negative Mood
- Unappreciation
- Instability and Uncertainty
- Autocratic Management Behavior

The development of toxic leadership research reveals how the concept manifests itself in different sectors and contexts. Since the pioneering work of Tepper (2000), the concept has been analysed in an increasingly comprehensive framework. Goldman's (2006) research on the relationship between personality disorders and organizational toxicity has contributed to our understanding of the psychological underpinnings of toxic leadership. Appelbaum and Roy-Girard (2007), who present striking findings on the organizational costs of toxic leadership, state that businesses in North America suffer an annual loss of 200 billion dollars due to behaviors associated with toxic leadership. In addition to this economic impact, the negative effects of toxic leadership on employees' psychological capital are also reported widely in the literature (Pelletier, 2010). Steele (2011), in a study conducted in the US Army, found that one out of every five subordinates perceived their leaders as toxic and revealed that toxic leaders exhibit behaviors such as micro-management, aggressive attitude, rigidity and weakness in decision-making. Kırbaç (2013), in his study conducted in educational institutions, emphasised that toxic leaders mask their unethical behaviors by using their achievements and this leads to the emergence of toxic school culture. Chua and Murray's (2015) study provide important findings from a gender perspective. It was found that women perceived toxic leaders more negatively than men and were concerned more about the negative connotations of messages. This finding emphasizes the importance of gender differences in toxic leadership perception. Turkish studies expanded the concept's dimensionality. Çelebi et al. (2015) developed a four-dimensional toxic leadership scale based on teacher perceptions: selfishness, self-interest, negative mental state, and unappreciation. Author (2016) extended this framework to a five-dimensional structure, identifying sectoral variations between manufacturing and accommodation industries. Reyhanoğlu and Akın's (2016) conceptual analysis demonstrated how toxic leaders' abusive, narcissistic, and authoritarian traits negatively impact both employee wellbeing and organizational health.

Recent studies have examined toxic leadership relationships with diverse organizational variables. Çetinkaya (2017) established toxic leadership dimensions as significant predictors of teacher burnout, while Özer et al. (2017) identified demographic variations in healthcare professionals' toxic leadership perceptions. Akça (2017) and Yalçınsoy and Işık (2018) demonstrated positive correlations between toxic leadership and turnover intention. Health sector research reveals multidimensional effects: Koç et al. (2022) found toxic leadership induces emotional exhaustion, with intrinsic motivation serving as a moderating variable. Reyhanoğlu and Akın's (2020) hospital employee study revealed toxic leadership negatively impacts organizational justice while positively influencing organizational silence and turnover intention, with differential effects between temporary and permanent staff. Guo et al.'s (2022) qualitative Chinese study identified nurse managers' toxic leadership manifesting through negative feedback, ignoring behaviors, unfair treatment, excessive pressure, and egocentrism. Higher education research by Dahlan et al. (2024) demonstrated toxic leadership's negative effects on academic and administrative staff commitment, loyalty, and satisfaction. Ronnie (2024) found that toxic leadership makes it difficult to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals, while ethical leadership and strategic Human Resources Management practices can play an important role in reducing this negative impact.

Studies focusing on the tourism industry reveal the unique dynamics of the sector. Hoel and Einarsen's (2003) pioneering study highlighted the importance of systematic studies related to violence and stress in the tourism industry. Mathisen et al. (2008) found a negative relationship between bullying and job satisfaction and creativity in the restaurant industry, and a positive relationship with burnout and intention to quit. Bloisi and Hoel's (2008) finding that abusive management in culinary culture is normalized was supported by Alexander et al.'s (2011) research. Bentley et al. (2011) found that one out of every ten employees in the travel industry experienced bullying and emphasized that bullying affects not only the victims but also the employees who witness it. Civilidağ's (2014) study measures the prevalence of exposure to mobbing in hotel employees to be 15.8%. Ram (2015) finds that bullying negatively affects the image of the industry. These two studies when considered together demonstrate the individual and organizational dimensions of the problem. Furthermore, Ariza-Montes et al. (2017) found that the structural characteristics of the hospitality industry trigger bullying outbreaks. Studies conducted in the tourism sector during the COVID-19 pandemic show that the effects of toxic leadership become more pronounced in times of crisis. While Koo et al. (2022) found that toxic leadership negatively affects employee resilience and crisis communication, Wolor et al. (2022) found that negative effects on job satisfaction and motivation indirectly affect employee performance. Emphasizing that toxic leadership in the digital age is evolving into a new form of authoritarian management (digital authoritarianism), Ott and Hoelscher (2023) state that social media platforms make these behaviors more visible.

2.2. Cognitive Mapping Method

The cognitive mapping method is a qualitative research approach that allows individuals' cognitive models to be visualized in a systematic framework. The theoretical basis of the method is based on Kelly's (1991) Personal Construct Theory. According to this theory, individuals make sense of the world through contrast and similarity, establish causal relationships and organize concepts hierarchically (Fuglseth & Gronhaug, 2002). Cognitive maps provide a visual representation of the concepts that individuals create in their own minds in perceiving and making sense of the phenomena around them and the relationships between these concepts (Kalburan et al., 2018). The term cognitive mapping was first used by Tolman in 1948, but the basis of the method is based on Euler's "Graph Theory" in 1736. Developed in 1976 by Axelrod, the method provides a powerful tool for the systematic analysis of individuals' cognitive models (Eden, 1988).

Structurally, cognitive maps can be constructed in three different types: concept maps, semantic maps and cause-effect maps (Siau & Tan, 2005). In this study, cause-effect maps were used. Cause-and-effect maps are seen as a means of exploring individuals' unique beliefs in a particular domain (Nadkarni & Narayanan, 2005). These maps allow to define causal relationships between concepts by clustering complex systems. The most important feature of the method is that it clearly reveals the concepts in the participant's mind and the causal relationship between these concepts (Markoczy, 1994). Cause-effect maps have a hierarchical structure and the concepts of "head" and "tail" play an important role in this structure. According to Eden and Ackermann (2004), head concepts are concepts that do not follow another concept and are often expressed as goals; that is, they represent desired or undesired end results. Tail concepts, on the other hand, are clues that lead to these outcomes, which are not defined by more concepts. A sample cause and effect map and the location of the head and tail concepts on the map are given in Figure 1. Cognitive mapping method has been successfully applied in different research areas. For example, Klein and Cooper (1982) examined military decision-making processes, Atasoy (2007) examined the success of construction projects, Author (2009) examined strategy development processes, and Abat (2010) examined educational management competences with this method. In recent years, Tuncer and Tuncer (2017) analysed public relations decisions and Kalburan et al. (2018) analysed the factors affecting internet shopping with the cognitive mapping method.

There are some basic elements to ensure the validity and reliability of the method. According to Fuglseth and Gronhaug (2002), the compatibility of the theory-method-data trilogy is important. Ambrosini and Bowman (2005) emphasize that enabling the participants to fully reflect their own thoughts increases validity. Axelrod (1976) states that concepts and causal relationships should come from data, not from researcher assumptions (Fuglseth and Gronhaug 2002).

Cognitive mapping offers an effective tool for understanding and visualising complex networks of relationships. This method provides the opportunity to systematically analyze the perceptions and experiences of individuals in a human-oriented and multidimensional field such as tourism. The demonstration of cause-effect relationships contributes to a deeper understanding of the research problem.

Figure 1: Head and Tail Concept in Cause and Effect Maps

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Purpose of the Research and Problem Development

Toxic leaders are defined as individuals who cause serious and permanent damage to individuals, groups, organizations and communities with their destructive behaviors, dysfunctional personalities and characteristics. The presence of such leaders damages the organization in many ways (Başar et al., 2016). It is also seen that toxic leaders are costly for organizations. It has been reported that companies in the US alone suffer \$200 billion in losses annually due to toxicity in the workplace, including toxic leader behaviors (Appelbaum & Roy-Girard, 2007).

In the tourism industry, which is labor-intensive, especially in accommodation and food and beverage businesses, the main element that produces and provides services is human labor (Kozak et al., 2017). For this reason, the negative situations that an employee is exposed to also directly affect the service recipient. Therefore, it is important to determine the behaviors of toxic leaders on their employees and establish cause-effect relationships of these behaviors. For these reasons, the main problem of the study is determined as "What are the toxic leadership behaviors perceived by the students?". The following reasons were effective in determining the sub-problems:

In the studies conducted by Alexander et al. (2011) and Bloisi and Hoel (2008), it was found that verbal bullying and abusive management practices were accepted as a natural part of the culinary culture, especially in the kitchen department. This situation reveals the need to examine the differences in perceptions especially between Gastronomy and Culinary Arts and Hospitality Management departments. In the study conducted by Taftaf (2018), it was concluded that female students perceived higher levels of mistreatment than male students. Similarly, Chua and Murray (2015) found that women perceived toxic leadership more negatively than men. In the literature, it has been determined that toxic leadership have several negative effects on employees such as loss of trust in the workplace, unhealthy communication, damage to organizational commitment (Yalçınsoy & Işık, 2018), increase in intention to quit (Sezici, 2016), decrease in employee productivity and high absenteeism rate (Author, 2016). These findings show the necessity to examine whether experiences with toxic leaders create perception differences.

In line with these reasons, the sub-problems of the research were determined as follows:

- Are there similarities and differences between students' perceptions of toxic leadership?
- Do students' perceptions of toxic leadership differ by the department they study in?
- Do students' perceptions of toxic leadership differ by their gender?
- Do students' perceptions of toxic leadership differ by their experiences with toxic leaders?

3.2. Research Method

Cognitive Mapping Method was used in this research which was designed as a qualitative case study. Laddering interview technique was used to obtain cognitive maps and cognitive maps were created using Decision Explorer 3.3.0 software. Central, Cluster, Hieset, Potency and Collapse Analyses were performed on the obtained maps.

3.2.1. Data Collection Process

The sample of the study of 40 students studying at Kocaeli University Faculty of Tourism in Türkiye were selected by convenience sampling method. Participants were selected equally from the departments of Hospitality Management (n=20) and Gastronomy and Culinary Arts (n=20). In the literature, it is seen that the sample size of the studies using cognitive mapping method is generally low (e.g., Atasoy, 2007: n=3; Author, 2009: n=6; Abat, 2010: n=6). The data was collected through interviews conducted in an environment where the participant and the researcher were alone. This approach aimed to reveal individual perceptions more clearly by preventing the participants from being affected by the presence of other participants. The interviews lasted a minimum of 20 minutes and a maximum of 85 minutes, and the average interview duration was recorded as 41 minutes. Total interview time was 27 hours and 36 minutes. In this process, the behaviors of people in managerial and supervisory positions were also evaluated with the assumption that these also constitute leader behaviors. In addition to the interviews, the participants were asked to fill out a questionnaire to indicate their demographic characteristics.

The data collection process was carried out in three stages with a systematic approach:

- *In the first stage*, the participants were asked the question "Who is a toxic leader in your opinion and what behaviors does he/she exhibit?" in an organizational context. Each action stated by the participants was simultaneously recorded on the computer using Decision Explorer 3.3.0 program.
- *In the second stage* the question "How?" was asked for each action expressed by the participants in accordance with the laddering interview technique. This question aimed to understand how the stated action was performed. The answers given to the "How" question formed the sub-concepts of the first stated action. This process until the participant had no answer to the "How" question.
- *In the third stage*, the question "Why?" by returning to the first concepts. The answers to the question "Why?" revealed the consequences of the toxic leader's behaviors, leading to higher concepts, and finally the main concept of "She/He is a toxic leader" was reached. As stated by Eden and Ackermann (2004), this approach enabled a concept to be given meaning not only through its content but also through the consequences attributed to it and the explanatory concepts supporting it. In order to ensure data reliability, participants were given the opportunity to check the created maps and correct possible missing relationships both during and at the end of the interview.

3.2.2. Creating Group Models Related to Research Problems

In order to seek answers to the problems of the study, the combination method was used in the formation of group models. This process was carried out in four stages with a systematic approach:

Limitation of Cognitive Content: 1193 concepts obtained from 40 participants were reduced to 145 concepts by combining similar expressions that repeated at least twice. As suggested by Laukkanen (1994) and Markoczy (1994), the maps were drawn by giving general labels to the concepts used by the participants. With reference to Eden and Ackermann's (2004) approach, the meaning of each merged concept was expanded and different causal relationships were taken into account.

Establishing Reliability: The process of coding and combining the concepts was carried out with the principle of unanimity or majority vote of three experts (the researcher, another researcher working on the same method and the thesis advisor). This approach ensured the objectivity of the coding process.

Model Building: In the first stage, a common group model including the data of all participants was created. Then, six different group models were developed according to demographic variables:

Comparative Analysis: The models were analysed comparatively to identify similarities and differences in perceptions of toxic leadership. This analysis allowed for a systematic examination of interdepartmental, gender-based and experience-based perception differences.

3.2.3. Data Analysis

Decision Explorer 3.3.0 software was used to create cognitive maps, construct group models and perform structural analyses. This software is described as an effective tool in qualitative data analysis (Decision Explorer® User's Guide, 2017: 14) and is widely preferred in cognitive mapping research. The methodological validity of Decision Explorer has been tested previously in various research contexts. For example, Author (2009) used it in strategy development processes, Abat (2010) in educational management research, Goodier and Soetanto (2013) in scenario planning, and Pyrko and Dörfler (2018) in analyzing managerial decision-making processes. Eden and Ackermann (2004) and Vangen and Huxham (2011) demonstrated the effectiveness of the software in analyzing complex cognitive structures.

Systematic structural analyses were performed on seven different group models created in the research. For each model, central, cluster, hieset, potency and collapse analyses were applied. This comprehensive analysis process allowed for a detailed examination of the different dimensions of toxic leadership perception and the differences between groups.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Common-group Model Results

The common group model reflecting the toxic leadership perceptions of all participants (n=40) consisted of 142 concepts. As a result of the Collapse analysis, which includes the summary findings of all analyses, this complex structure was distilled to 15 core concepts. In the Collapse analysis, the following data were collapsed into one and the most important concepts of the Common Group Model were color coded and visualized in a summary model: *head concept* of the model and the first *five concepts of the central* analysis, the *head concepts of the clusters* obtained as a result of the cluster analysis and the *clue/tail*

concepts in more than one *hieset* obtained as a result of the *potency* analysis. The central analysis revealed that the behavior of demotivating employees was the most influential factor on students' perception of toxic leadership. This effect is followed by the behaviors of disregarding the rights of employees, not treating employees as human beings, discrimination and making employees feel bad. The relationships between these behaviors, which are shown in Figure 2, reflect the toxic leadership perception of all participants. And the concept of a toxic leader is also head concept of the common group model.

Figure 2: Common Group Model Collapse Analysis Result

The analyses made in the other group models are also summarized in the same way through collapse analysis. Therefore, a summarized view is reached showing the key points in students' perceptions of toxic leadership in the context of the group models, the dimensions in which they explain toxic leadership, data on which actions serve these dimensions and the effective clues giving away a toxic leader.

4.2. Toxic Leadership Perceptions Differentiated According to the Department of Study

One half of the participants are studying in the department of Hospitality Management and the other half in the department of Gastronomy and Culinary Arts. As a result of the analyses performed on the group models of the students of both departments, it was determined that their perceptions of toxic leadership differed. Cognitive maps showing the results of collapse analyses are presented in Figures 3 and 4. The differing perceptions according to the department of study are presented in Table 1. In Figure 3, analysis findings are coded with different colors and the group model consisting of 76 concepts in total is summarized with 30 concepts. Likewise, in Figure 4, a summary model including the most important expressions of the group model is visualized by explaining the group model consisting of 77 concepts with 6 concepts, in which the analysis findings are coded with separate colors.

Figure 3: Hospitality Management Students Collapse Analysis Results

Figure 4: Gastronomy and Culinary Arts Students Collapse Analysis Results

Table 1. Toxic Leadership Perceptions According to the Department of Study

Hospitality Management	Gastronomy and Culinary Arts
Reduces employee motivation	Reduces employee motivation
Disregards the rights of employees	Disregards the rights of employees
Makes the employee feel bad	Discriminates between employees
Causes delays	Does not treat employees as human beings
Reduces the efficiency of work	Reduces employee performance
Does not empathise with employees	Does not pay overtime
Reflects his/her private life at work	
Makes you work overtime	
Does not pay overtime	
Uses imperative language	
Does not treat employees as human beings	
Not interested in employees' problems	
Only deems what he/she already knows as true	
Lacks self-confidence	
Sets strict rules	
Does not pay salaries on time	
Does not give employees the wages they deserve	
Behaves badly when the employee makes a mistake	
Does not ensure communication between employees	
Does not care about own outer appearance	
Does not care about the private life of the employee	
Does not pay attention to entry and exit times	
Does not attach importance to the opinions of employees	
Does not care about days off	
Does not register employees to the social security institution	
Does not take risks	
Implements only his own decisions	
Does not treat employees equally	
Speaks loudly	
Decides alone	

Source: Created by the authors.

As seen in Table 1, the most important toxic leader behaviors perceived by the students of both departments are "decreases employee motivation" and "disregards the rights of the employees". However, the reasons underlying these behaviors differ between the departments. For Gastronomy and Culinary Arts students, disregarding the rights of employees is associated with the unequal distribution of break times in addition to the negative behaviors related to wages, insurance, working hours and leave days. These negative behaviors related to break times also result in discrimination by the toxic leader. In the group model of Hospitality Management students, no statements related to break times were found.

The behavior "makes the employee feel bad" is more important for Hospitality Management students than Gastronomy and Culinary Arts students. However, Hospitality Management students attach more importance to the toxic leader's behaviors that negatively affect the "quality of work". When evaluated in the context of Fiedler's situational leadership approach, it is seen that Hospitality Management students give importance to both leader-follower relations and the quality of work, while Gastronomy and Culinary

Arts students mainly focus on leader-follower relations.

Differences were also found between departments in terms of communication style. For Hospitality Management students the leader's shouting and commanding behavior offends negatively affects their psychology, motivation and productivity. In the statements of Gastronomy and Culinary Arts students, the leader's shouting is not encountered, while the leader's commanding tone does not have a negative effect on motivation and productivity.

4.3. Toxic Leadership Perceptions Differentiated by Gender

The participants of 50% female and 50% male students. The toxic leadership perceptions of both gender groups were analysed and significant differences were found. Cognitive maps showing the results of collapse analyses are given in Figures 5 and 6. Perceptions differing according to gender are presented in Table 2. Figure 5 shows a summary map including the most important expressions of the group model consisting of 81 concepts including the expressions of female students and demonstrates the most important expressions identified in the group model with 12 main concepts.

Figure 5: Female Students Collapse Analysis Results

Figure 6: Male Students Collapse Analysis Results

Table 2: Toxic Leadership Perceptions by Gender

Female Students	Male Students
Reduces employee motivation	Reduces employee motivation
Disregards the rights of employees	Disregards the rights of employees
Discriminates between employees	Reduces the efficiency of work
Is unjust	Does not treat employees as human beings
Makes the employee feel bad	Does not empathize with employees
Makes you work overtime	
Does not give employees the wages they deserve	
Does not pay salaries on time	
Does not distribute salaries equally	
Does not let employees use their leave days	
Applies break times differently according to the habits of the employee	
Does not raise wages	

Source: Created by the authors.

Female students define toxic leadership with more multidimensional behaviors than male students. For both groups, the most important toxic leader behavior is determined as "demotivating employees". However, the demotivating factors differ according to gender. For female students, wage-related factors (not being paid the wages they deserve, not being paid on time, wages not being distributed equally and not receiving raises) are among the main reasons for demotivation. This result shows that female students attach more importance to financial aspects than male students.

Female students' perception of organizational justice is higher than that of male students. While the discriminatory behavior of the toxic leader is explained by actions such as inequality of distance in relationships, inequality of workload, salary and break times for women, such a detailed definition of discrimination is not found in the map of male students. Male students perceived the self-centeredness and self-interest dimensions of the toxic leader at a higher degree. In addition, male students associate the concepts of "human value and empathy" with more negative actions and perceive the dimension of toxic leader's ignorance of values to a higher degree than female students. In the context of Fiedler's situational leadership approach, male students give importance to both leader-follower relationships and the quality of work, while female students focus mainly on leader-follower relationships.

4.4. Toxic Leadership Perceptions Differentiated According to Toxic Leader Experience

While 58% of the participants had worked with a toxic leader before, 42% had not. Significant differences were found between the toxic leadership perceptions of the experienced and inexperienced groups. Cognitive maps showing the results of collapse analyses are given in Figures 7 and 8. Perceptions differing according to toxic leader experience are presented in Table 3. Figure 7 summarizes the 95 concepts in the group model with 9 core concepts as a result of collapse analysis. Figure 8 summarizes the 62 concepts in the group model of the students without toxic leader experience with 10 core concepts as a result of collapse analysis.

Figure 7. Students With Toxic Leader Experience Collapse Analysis Results

Figure 8. Students Without Toxic Leader Experience Collapse Analysis Results

Table 3: Toxic Leader Perceptions According to Toxic Leader Experience

With Toxic Leader Experience	No Toxic Leader Experience
Reduces employee motivation	Reduces employee motivation
Has an unhealthy communication with employees	Disregards the rights of employees
Disregards the rights of employees	Causes the employee to quit the job
Is unjust	Discriminates between employees
Does not protect employee rights	Make employees feel bad
Discriminates between employees	Does not pay overtime
Underestimates its employees	Does not pay salaries on time
Does not give employees the wage they deserve	Does not give employees the wage they deserve
Makes you work overtime	Does not let employees use their leave days
	Applies break times differently according to the habits of the employees

Source: Created by the authors.

For students with toxic leader experience, the most important factor after motivation was found to be “has an unhealthy relationship with employees”. This group attributes higher importance to leader-employee communication before material and moral rights. Unhealthy communication manifests itself in the form of not dealing with problems, not caring about employees, and not being able to ensure communication between employees, which discourages employees and decreases their motivation. In the perception of students without toxic leadership experience, the statement “causes employees to quit their jobs” stands out. This behavior emerges as a result of low motivation, not dealing with problems, mobbing and disregarding rights. It is noteworthy that there are no statements related to leaving the job in the experienced group. “Underestimates employees” behavior was more important in the experienced toxic leader group. For this group, belittling is associated with behaviors such as not treating as a human being, abusive and slang language, shouting and giving orders continuously. In the inexperienced group, contemptuous behaviors other than speaking in imperative mode were not observed. In both groups, the concept of “between employees” is important. However, for the experienced group, this concept is in a circular relationship with the concept of “unfair” and is explained with more specific types of discrimination such as gender, religion/language/race discrimination. An important behavior expressed by the experienced toxic leader group alone is the behavior of “not protecting the rights of employees by turning a blind eye to the injustices done to the employees in his/her unit”. This behavior causes employees to become disenchanted and demotivated. These findings show that toxic leader experience significantly shapes students' perceptions and the group with experience of working with a toxic leader has a more detailed and multidimensional perception of toxic leadership.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

5.1. Impact on Employee Motivation

The key finding of the study is that behaviors reducing employee motivation are the most influential factor on students' perception of toxic leadership. This result is in line with Başar et al.'s (2016) study, which revealed that the dark side of leadership causes psychological effects on employees. In the recent literature, Koç et al. (2022)'s study in the health sector also revealed similar results and found that toxic leadership causes emotional exhaustion of employees, but intrinsic motivation plays a mitigating role in this effect. This finding suggests that motivation can be a stabilising factor for toxic leadership effects in different sectors. At the same time, it supports the research of Çetin et al. (2017), which states that employees' motivation and performance are affected by leadership style. It is also compatible with the behavior of sabotaging the motivation of employees, which is emphasized in Einarsen et al. (2007)'s research defining the concept of destructive leadership.

Among the factors affecting motivation, basic rights (wages, insurance, overtime, days off, break periods) and psychological factors (unhealthy communication, not being appreciated, not being given promotions) were identified. These factors were found to correspond to the first three steps in Maslow's hierarchy of needs and hygiene factors in Herzberg's two-factor theory. This result, which is consistent with the research of Alkış and Öztürk (2009) in which they determined that Herzberg's hygiene factors can be used

as a motivational tool in hospitality businesses, shows that having a toxic leader is a strong obstacle in the motivation of all tourism students participating in the research, regardless of the department of study, gender and toxic leader experience.

Koo et al. (2022) found that toxic leadership negatively affects employee resilience and crisis communication during times of crisis. Similarly, Wolor et al.'s (2022) research demonstrates the multidimensional nature of this effect by revealing that the negative effects of toxic leadership on job satisfaction and motivation indirectly affect employee performance. In Dahlan et al.'s (2024) study in higher education institutions, the finding that the commitment and satisfaction of academic and administrative staff are negatively affected by toxic leadership confirms that the negative impact of toxic leadership on motivation is a cross-sectoral problem.

5.2. Differences in Perception According to the Department of Study

One of the most important results that emerged in the context of the department of study is the concept of "disregarding the rights of the employees". According to Gastronomy and Culinary Arts students, the negative attributes related to wages, insurance, working hours and days off, as well as the negative attributes related to the flexibility of break times are important clues that the toxic leader disregards the rights of employees. These findings also serve the discrimination perception of gastronomy students and it was determined that they perceived discrimination behavior more than hospitality management students. This finding is in line with a similar situation in a Tokyo-based marketing company (www.businessinsider.com, 2017). Flexibility in break times was accepted as an indicator of discrimination by the employees and led to an adjustment in the company policy.

The behavior "does not regard employees as human beings", which is perceived in common by the students of both departments, is manifested in different ways. In the map of Gastronomy and Culinary Arts students, the leader's behavior of not regarding employees as human beings manifests in the form of not caring about the employees and their problems, seeing himself/herself superior to the employees and attributing the responsibilities of his/her own mistakes to subordinates. These behaviors overlap with Schmidt's (2008) narcissism dimension, Çelebi et al.'s (2015) self-interest dimension, and Author's (2016) value ignorance dimension. In the perception of Hospitality Management students, the behavior of not treating employees as human beings is mostly associated with underestimation. This result is explained by the unappreciative dimension of the toxic leadership revealed by Çelebi et al. (2015) and Author (2016) in their studies.

Remarkable differences were found between the departments in terms of communication style. For Hospitality Management students, the leader's shouting and commanding behavior is perceived as a type of behavior that offends employees, negatively affects their performance and undermines motivation. On the other hand, Gastronomy and Culinary Arts students did not perceive shouting behavior as significant and did not perceive a negative effect of commanding behavior on motivation and productivity. This result is in line with the findings of Alexander et al. (2011) and Bloisi and Hoel (2008) who found that "verbal bullying is normalized in culinary culture". It is also in line with the findings of Hoel and Einarsen (2003), who stated that the potential cause of aggression and bullying in the kitchen is the crowded, noisy and hot work environment in the kitchen.

It was determined that Hospitality Management students gave more importance to the action "makes the employee feel bad" than Gastronomy and Culinary Arts students. This result is in line with the research of Author (2016), who found that autocratic management behavior is more common in the hospitality sector.

When evaluated in the context of Fiedler's situational leadership approach, it was determined that Hospitality Management students attach importance to both leader-follower relationships and behaviors that affect the quality of work. For these students, the behaviors of "causes delays" and "reduces the efficiency of work" are more prominent than Gastronomy and Culinary Arts students. It is seen that Gastronomy and Culinary Arts students mainly focus on leader-follower relations. This difference may be due to the operational structures of the departments. The fact that direct interaction with customers is more intense in hospitality businesses may increase the importance given to the non-disturbance of business processes. The negative feedback, ignoring, unfair treatment and excessive pressure behaviors found in Guo et al.'s (2022) qualitative study on nurse managers in China are similar to the toxic leadership behaviors perceived by Hospitality Management students in our study.

5.3. Perception Differences According to Gender

According to the results of the study female students express toxic leadership with more multidimensional behaviors than male students. This result is in line with Taftaf (2018)'s finding that female students perceive higher levels of mistreatment than male students and Chua and Murray (2015)'s findings that women perceive toxic leadership more negatively than men. Among the actions that undermine women's motivation, it is seen that statements related to salary are more common than men. This result is in line with Küçük (2015)'s finding that women's strongest expectation in business life is the desire to be economically strong and Bayram (2017)'s finding that financial incentives increase the motivation of women tour guides more than men.

Reyhanoğlu and Akın's (2020) research on hospital employees revealed that toxic leadership negatively affects organizational justice. This finding coincides with the result of this study that especially female students show high organizational justice sensitivity. In addition, in this study, it was found that female students' perception of organizational justice was higher than male students. This result is consistent with the findings of Author (2010) that women's perceptions of organizational justice are higher than men in his study on hotel employees. Uysal and Tayfun (2019)'s finding that the motivation levels of hotel business employees decrease when their perception of organizational justice is negative was also confirmed in this study.

The fact that Çetinkaya (2017) and Demirel (2015) did not find a significant difference according to gender in their studies on teachers shows that the effect of gender on toxic leadership perception may vary according to the sector. Although Demirel (2015) did not find significant differences in the statements related to selfishness and self-interest, which are sub-dimensions of toxic leadership, one of the remarkable findings of this study is that the self-interest dimension of toxic leadership differs according to gender. While male students defined the toxic leader with the behaviors of "blames the responsibility of own failures on the employees" and "only takes credit for success", these statements were not found in the perceptions of female students. This result shows that male students perceive the self-interest dimension of the toxic leader to a higher degree and this coincides with the findings obtained by Eriş and Arun (2020) from male bank employees. The concepts of "human values and empathy" stand out in the perception of male students. Male students associated these concepts with more negative actions compared to female students and attributed more importance to these behaviors in the perception of toxic leadership. This finding shows that male students perceive the value ignorance dimension of toxic leadership to a higher degree. In the context of Fiedler's situational leadership approach, it was found that male students focused on both leader-follower relationships and the quality of work (productivity, performance), whereas female students mainly focused on leader-follower relationships.

5.4. Perception Differences According to Toxic Leader Experience

In the comparison according to toxic leader experience, it was observed that students with experience place higher importance to communication with the leader before material and moral rights. This result is in line with Wilson-Starks' (2003) view that people have intrinsic value beyond their salary or position and are more productive when they are treated as human beings.

It was determined that the toxic leadership perception of the students who did not have toxic leader experience differed with the statement "causes the employee to quit the job". This result is important because the fact that those who have toxic leader experience continue to work with them may cause the toxicity they are exposed to to go unnoticed by the leader, and it can even be said that employees serve the toxic behaviors of the leader without being aware of it. At the same time, this finding of the study is in line with the studies of Sezici (2016), Akça (2017), Lavoie- Tremblay et al. (2016) and Yalçınsoy and Işık (2018), who found a positive relationship between toxic leadership, destructive leadership and abusive management practices and intention to quit.

The perception of discrimination was identified as an important factor in both groups. However, in the experienced group, the concept of discrimination is in a circular relationship with "injustice" and is explained with more specific dimensions such as gender, religion/language/race discrimination. These findings coincide with the dimension of "promotion of inequality" that Pelletier (2010) revealed in his research with those who directly experienced toxic leadership. In addition, the behavior of "not protecting employees' rights", which was particularly emphasised by the experienced group, was associated with the leader's turning a blind eye to the injustices done to the employees in his/her unit. The importance given by experienced students to the behavior of "belittling employees" is remarkable. This behavior is associated

with actions such as not treating as a human being, abusive speech, shouting and giving orders continuously and is explained with different dimensions in the literature: Çelebi et al. (2015) and Author (2016) discussed it within the dimension of unappreciation, Schmidt (2008) and Pelletier (2010) within the dimension of abusive management, and Başar and Sıgır (2016) within the scope of bullying behaviors of destructive leadership.

5.5. Theoretical and Practical Contributions of the Research

5.6.1. Theoretical Contributions

This study makes several theoretical contributions to the toxic leadership literature in the tourism sector. Firstly, it sheds light on the impact of the structural characteristics of the industry on leadership perceptions by revealing how toxic leadership perceptions differ across departments. In particular, the role of the unique dynamics of gastronomy and hospitality management departments in the perception and normalization of toxic leadership behaviors offers a new perspective to the literature.

By analyzing gender-based differences in toxic leadership perceptions in detail, the study clarifies contradictory findings in the existing literature in the tourism context. In particular, the systematic analysis of the importance that male and female students attribute to different dimensions of toxic leadership deepens the theoretical understanding.

This study offers a methodological innovation by using cognitive mapping to analyze the effect of previous toxic leader experience to toxic leader perception. This approach provides a new analytical framework for understanding how prior experience shapes and normalizes perceptions of toxic leadership.

5.6.2. Practical contributions

Implications for Tourism Organizations: Study findings emphasize the necessity of department-specific approaches in designing leadership development programs in tourism enterprises. In this context:

- Establishment of department-based communication protocols
- Developing systematic policies for the protection of employee rights
- Adopting gender-sensitive management approaches

Implications for Educational Institutions: Increasing toxic leadership awareness in the curricula of tourism education institutions is one of the important practical implications of the research.

In this context, following topics can be added to the curricula:

- Development of department-specific leadership styles
- Examination of toxic leadership scenarios through case studies
- It is recommended to evaluate internship experiences from a leadership perspective.

Implications for Sector Leaders:

- Regular assessment and review of leadership practices
- Developing fair and transparent management systems that take into account departmental differences
- Adopting communication strategies that support employee motivation.

The implementation of these practical implications will contribute to preventing toxic leadership and increasing employee motivation in tourism organizations. The departmental, gender and experience-based differences revealed in this study can be used to support the sustainable success of organizations.

5.6.3. Limitations of the Study and Suggestions for Future Research

This study was designed as a qualitative case study using cognitive mapping methodology. Due to the nature of the methodological approach, the generalizability of the findings has certain limitations. The fact that the research was conducted in the tourism faculty of a single university constitutes the limitation of the geographical and institutional context. However, cognitive structures are internal processes specific to individuals. Cognitive maps that visualize these processes are limited in the sense that they represent the cognitive structures as much as the participants reported. Future research could adopt the following approaches to overcome the methodological limitations of this study by incorporating the following:

- Use of mixed method designs
- Performing comparative case analyses
- Sample extension covering different universities and countries
- Examining the organizational consequences of toxic leadership on departmental level
- Comparison of toxic leadership dynamics in different tourism sub-sectors
- Analyzing the cross-cultural differences of toxic leadership perception
- Investigating the long-term career effects of toxic leadership experience
- Measuring the effects of toxic leadership on service quality
- Evaluation of the effectiveness of department-specific leadership development programs
- Testing intervention strategies to prevent toxic leadership
- Examining the effect of organizational policies and practices on toxic leadership

Research to be conducted in line with these recommendations can contribute to the development of toxic leadership literature in the tourism industry and the improvement of sectoral practices. In particular, to the methodological diversity and theoretical depth the enrichment of knowledge in the field.

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